

A/Miz.51 and PMS3 A/Saruchina were more efficient at flowering. PMS3 A/Saruchina recorded the highest total dry matter (12.1 t/ha) and grain yield (538 g/m²)

Fertilizer management

Integrated effect of deeply placed urea and *Gliricidia* green manure on grain yield of transplanted rice

S. S. Dhane, R. R. Khadse, and H. K. Pawar, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Karjat, Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli, Maharashtra 410201, India

We studied the integrated effect of organic and inorganic sources of N on grain yield of rice variety PLG-1 (130 d duration) during 1991-93 wet seasons. We compared how deeply placing urea behind the plow and applying *Gliricidia sepium* leaves as a green manure—individually and in combination—affected rainfed transplanted rice.

Each of the nine treatments in the experiment was laid out in a 50-m² plot on the RARS farm in a randomized block design with three replications. The soil was clay loam with pH 7.4 (1:2.5 soil:water) and a cation exchange capacity of 35 meq/100 g soil. All of the plots received 21 kg P/ha as single superphosphate and 41 kg K/ha as potassium chloride.

Prilled urea (PU) (25 kg N and 50 kg N/ha) was applied behind the plow, about 5-6 cm deep, at the time of puddling. *Gliricidia* was spread uniformly over newly puddled soil as fresh green manure at 5 and 10 t/ha (containing 2.7% N on an oven-dry basis)

Effect of integrated use of inorganic and organic N on grain yield of rice. Maharashtra, India.

followed by IR64 A/Miz.51. Photosynthesis at flowering, however, was positively correlated with total dry matter ($r = 0.430^*$) and grain yield ($r = 0.446^*$) at harvest.

Unlike PMS3 A/Saruchina, high Pn coupled with low MR and high Pn/MR are desirable for high photosynthetic productivity, which ultimately leads to more grain. ■

Effect of deeply placed urea behind the plow and *Gliricidia* green manure on grain yield of transplanted rice. Maharashtra, India. 1991-93 wet seasons.

Treatment			Mean grain yield (t/ha)			
Urea N (kg/ha)	Green manure (t/ha)	(kg N/ha)	1991	1992	1993	Pooled mean
0	0	0	4.0	2.2	3.7	3.3
25	0	0	4.9	2.8	4.4	4.0
50	0	0	4.5	3.9	3.9	4.1
0	5	31.5	5.0	2.5	4.2	3.9
0	10	63.0	4.8	3.0	4.8	4.2
25	5	31.5	5.2	3.5	4.8	4.5
25	10	63.0	4.9	3.9	5.1	4.6
50	5	31.5	5.0	4.6	4.7	4.8
50	10	63.0	5.4	4.8	5.5	5.2
LSD (0.05)			ns ^a	0.4	0.4	0.1

^ans = not significant.

and pressed below the surface by hand. Three-week-old rice seedlings were planted at 20- × 15-cm² spacing during the wet season on 24 Jul 1991, 20 Jul 1992, and 19 Jul 1993 and harvested on 10 Nov 1991, 5 Nov 1992, and 3 Nov 1993.

The response of the rice crop to the different treatments varied significantly with the season (see table). Applying *Gliricidia* at 5 or 10 t/ha coupled with the deep placement of urea at 25 or 50 kg N/ha

increased rice grain yield significantly over applying *Gliricidia* alone. The maximum yield of 5.2 t/ha, which was significantly higher than the rest, was obtained by applying *Gliricidia* at 10 t/ha and urea at 50 kg N/ha (see table, figure). Thus, the integrated use of inorganic and organic nitrogen can make important contributions to increasing and sustaining rice production. ■

Effect of rice hull, biofertilizer, and chemical fertilizers on growth and nitrogen economy of wetland rice

T. K. Biswas, National Facility for Blue-Green Algal Collection, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India; and R. N. Garg, Agricultural Physics Department, IARI

We studied the effects on rice yield of using leucaena (*Leucaena leucifera*), a common leguminous plant in northern India; blue-green algae (BGA); and urea—individually and in combination—in a mild alkaline soil with and without rice hull amendment.

The soil was sandy loam (mixed, Isohyperthermic Typic Ustocrept) with pH 8.0, EC 4.2 dS/m, 22 kg ESP, CEC 15 cmol_c/kg, and 0.46% organic C. Rice hull (0.56% N on an oven-dry basis) was incorporated at 5 t/ha (about 22 kg N)

Effect of integrated use of biofertilizer and chemical fertilizer N on yield of Pusa Basmati 1. IARI, New Delhi, India. 1992 wet season.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Rice hull-amended field	Untreated field
Control	3.5	3.4
Blue-green algae (BGA)	3.9	3.8
Leucaena	4.9	4.7
Urea (30 kg N/ha)	3.8	4.0
Urea (60 kg N/ha)	4.4	4.1
Urea (120 kg N/ha)	5.1	5.0
Leucaena + BGA	4.9	4.7
Urea (30 kg N/ha) + BGA	4.6	3.9
Urea (60 kg N/ha) + BGA	5.0	4.8
1/2 Leucaena + urea (60 kg N/ha)	5.2	4.7
1/2 Leucaena + urea (90 kg N/ha)	5.4	5.0
CD (0.05)	0.4	0.5
Pooled mean	4.6	4.3
CD (0.05)		(0.7)